

Otopheidomenidae (Acari: Mesostigmata) – a new mite family for the fauna of Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula

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Abstract: A record of *Hemipteroseius adleri* Costa, 1968: the first member of family Otopheidomenidae (Acari) in Bulgaria, on *Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Hemiptera).

Key words: Acari, Otopheidomenidae, Hemiptera, *Pyrrhocoris apterus*, Bulgaria

Mites – ectoparasites on insects of the family Otopheidomenidae live as haemolymph sucking on Lepidoptera (Otopheidomeninae), Hemiptera Heteroptera (Treatiinae), Orthoptera (Katydidinae) and Isoptera (the genus *Eickworthius* Zhang, 1995) (PRASAD, 2011). Recently the specialist in Heteroptera Dr N. Simov found on the red firebug *Pyrrhocoris apterus* L. (Pyrrhocoridae), a very common species in Bulgaria, several mites belonging to Otopheidomenidae. The mites were found under the hemielytrae of the bugs and were identified as the species *Hemipteroseius adleri* Costa, described from Israel on the same bug species and on another one (*Scantius aegyptius* L.) by COSTA (1968). Later the species of Costa has been found in Europe (Poland, LEWANDOWSKI & SZAFRANEK, 2005), than also from Lithuania (CHMIELEWSKI, 2006a, 2006b), Hungary (KONTSCHAN & GYURIS, 2010) and Slovakia (FEND'A, 2011) – mostly in northern and central Europe. Other species of genus *Hemipteroseius* Evans, 1963 have been found on Pyrrhocoridae and Lygaeidae in Nigeria, India, Congo, Mexico, Jamaica, Cuba, Haiti, Puerto Rico, other Caribbean islands, and Panama – all of them in tropical countries (ZHANG, 1995).

Hemipteroseius adleri Costa, 1968 – many, Sofia, October 15th, 2013, N. Simov leg., P. Beron det.

The family is new for the fauna of Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula.

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Otopheidomenidae (Acari: Mesostigmata) – ново семейство акари за фауната на България и Балканския полуостров

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(Резюме)

Съобщава се за пръв път в България *Hemipteroseius adleri* по *Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Heteroptera: Pyrrhocoridae) – представител на новото за Балканския полуостров семейство акари Otopheidomenidae (Acari: Mesostigmata).